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Data management plan (DMP)

A Local Search Framework for Industrial Test Laboratory

Scheduling

EOSCSecretariat.eu

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	11/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project (deliverable xy)
2.0	11/05/2023	Second version of DMP – prepared for midterm review (deliverable xz)

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
TLSP	Test Laboratory Scheduling Problem
CP	Constraint Programming

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	050_782_60_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P2	055_782_90_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P3	055_782_90_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P4	055_782_90_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P5	055_782_90_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P6	000_88_5_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P7	001_88_5_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P8	001_88_5_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P9	005_88_10_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P10	005_88_10_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P11	005_88_10_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P12	005_88_10_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P13	000_88_5_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P14	000_88_5_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P15	000_88_5_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P16	001_88_5_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P17	001_88_5_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P18	006_88_10_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P19	006_88_10_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P20	006_88_10_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P21	006_88_10_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P22	010_174_20_environment.xml			100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P23	010_174_20_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P24	010_174_20_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P25	010_174_20_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P26	011_174_20_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P27	011_174_20_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P28	011_174_20_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P29	011_174_20_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P30	015_174_40_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P31	015_174_40_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P32	015_174_40_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P33	015_174_40_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P34	020_174_15_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P35	020_174_15_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P36	020_174_15_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P37	020_174_15_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P38	025_174_30_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P39	025_174_30_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P40	025_174_30_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P41	025_174_30_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P42	030_174_60_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P43	030_174_60_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P44	030_174_60_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P45	030_174_60_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P46	035_520_20_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P47	035_520_20_reference.xml			100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P48	035_520_20_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P49	035_520_20_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P50	040_520_40_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P51	040_520_40_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P52	040_520_40_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P53	040_520_40_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P54	045_520_60_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P55	045_520_60_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P56	045_520_60_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P57	045_520_60_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P58	050_782_60_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P59	050_782_60_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P60	050_782_60_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P61	050_782_60_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P62	055_782_90_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P63	055_782_90_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P64	055_782_90_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P65	055_782_90_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P66	000_88_5_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P67	000_88_5_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P68	000_88_5_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P69	000_88_5_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P70	001_88_5_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P71	001_88_5_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P72	001_88_5_schedule.xml			100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P73	001_88_5_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P74	005_88_10_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P75	005_88_10_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P76	005_88_10_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P77	005_88_10_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P78	006_88_10_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P79	006_88_10_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P80	006_88_10_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P81	006_88_10_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P82	010_174_20_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P83	010_174_20_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P84	010_174_20_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P85	010_174_20_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P86	011_174_20_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P87	011_174_20_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P88	011_174_20_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P89	011_174_20_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P90	015_174_40_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P91	015_174_40_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P92	015_174_40_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P93	015_174_40_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P94	020_174_15_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P95	020_174_15_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P96	020_174_15_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P97	020_174_15_tasks.xml			100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P98	025_174_30_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P99	025_174_30_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P100	025_174_30_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P101	025_174_30_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P102	030_174_60_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P103	030_174_60_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P104	030_174_60_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P105	030_174_60_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P106	035_520_20_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P107	035_520_20_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P108	035_520_20_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P109	035_520_20_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P110	040_520_40_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P111	040_520_40_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P112	040_520_40_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P113	040_520_40_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P114	Output_1.png	Images		100 MB	no
P115	Output_2.png	Images		100 MB	no
P116	Comparison of results.png	Images		100 MB	no
P117	The set of instances.png	Images		100 MB	no
P118	045_520_60_environment.xml			100 MB	no
P119	045_520_60_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P120	045_520_60_schedule.xml			100 MB	no
P121	045_520_60_tasks.xml			100 MB	no
P122	050_782_60_environment.xml			100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P123	050_782_60_reference.xml			100 MB	no
P124	050_782_60_schedule.xml			100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Real Life Data Set	https://www.dbai.tuwien.ac.at/staff/fmischek/TLSP/instances/RealWorld/		no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Nysret Musliu and Florian Mischek have been responsible for managing the project, identified by the project number 302:533-562. The project has received open access funding from TU Wien (TUW). The authors express their gratitude for the financial support provided by the Austrian Federal Ministry for Digital and Economic Affairs and the National Foundation for Research, Technology, and Development. This paper presents an instance generator for TLSP (Test Laboratory Scheduling Problem) that allows for the random generation of instances based on real-world data. The generator offers a range of configuration options to produce instances of various sizes and complexities as needed. It was implemented in Java. To generate a new instance, users specify the desired number of projects, the scheduling period's length, and optionally, other configuration parameters to fine-tune the instance properties. The instance generation process involves several steps. Firstly, the laboratory environment and available resources are defined based on the specified number of projects and scheduling period length. Next, the required number of projects and corresponding job sets are generated. These components are used to create a reference solution, ensuring a feasible solution for the final problem instance. The files are in the xlm format that has been created.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data. There are two sets of test data available, namely General and LabStructure, each consisting of 60 instances. Both data sets encompass instances of varying sizes, ranging from 5 projects over a span of 88 time slots to 90 projects over 782 time slots. On average, a single project comprises nearly 4 jobs. Initially, there are no specific assignments, except for a few jobs (approximately 5% of the total) that have predetermined assignments. These instances cover a planning period of around one and a half years and contain between 59 and 74 projects. As an illustration, consider the instance LabStructure/010, which consists of a total of 88 devices in equipment group 1. Out of these devices, job 45 requires 27 specific ones. In this scenario, there are approximately 3.3×10^{22} distinct equipment assignment possibilities for a particular job alone.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms. The data lacks metadata as it was randomly converted into .xml

and .xlsx formats, ensuring anonymity by omitting participant names and modules. While the data does not adhere to legal standards, tables prove to be the most valuable resource for comprehending the data. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

In terms of future work, there are plans to explore the applicability of the obtained results to the TLSP (Test Laboratory Scheduling Problem) that incorporates both TLSP-S and an additional grouping phase. Additionally, a promising research direction involves combining local search and CP-based approaches through hybrid algorithms or large neighbourhood search. This combination aims to leverage the strengths of both methods and enhance the results for TLSP-S even further.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done calibration, and standardised data capture.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

It has been paid strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	no access
P2	writing	writing	no access
P3	writing	writing	no access
P4	writing	writing	no access
P5	writing	writing	no access
P6	writing	writing	no access
P7	writing	writing	no access
P8	writing	writing	no access

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P9	writing	writing	no access
P10	writing	writing	no access
P11	writing	writing	no access
P12	writing	writing	no access
P13	writing	writing	no access
P14	writing	writing	no access
P15	writing	writing	no access
P16	writing	writing	no access
P17	writing	writing	no access
P18	writing	writing	no access
P19	writing	writing	no access
P20	writing	writing	no access
P21	writing	writing	no access
P22	writing	writing	no access
P23	writing	writing	no access
P24	writing	writing	no access
P25	writing	writing	no access
P26	writing	writing	no access
P27	writing	writing	no access
P28	writing	writing	no access
P29	writing	writing	no access
P30	writing	writing	no access
P31	writing	writing	no access
P32	writing	writing	no access
P33	writing	writing	no access

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P34	writing	writing	no access
P35	writing	writing	no access
P36	writing	writing	no access
P37	writing	writing	no access
P38	writing	writing	no access
P39	writing	writing	no access
P40	writing	writing	no access
P41	writing	writing	no access
P42	writing	writing	no access
P43	writing	writing	no access
P44	writing	writing	no access
P45	writing	writing	no access
P46	writing	writing	no access
P47	writing	writing	no access
P48	writing	writing	no access
P49	writing	writing	no access
P50	writing	writing	no access
P51	writing	writing	no access
P52	writing	writing	no access
P53	writing	writing	no access
P54	writing	writing	no access
P55	writing	writing	no access
P56	writing	writing	no access
P57	writing	writing	no access
P58	writing	writing	no access

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P59	writing	writing	no access
P60	writing	writing	no access
P61	writing	writing	no access
P62	writing	writing	no access
P63	writing	writing	no access
P64	writing	writing	no access
P65	writing	writing	no access
P66	writing	writing	no access
P67	writing	writing	no access
P68	writing	writing	no access
P69	writing	writing	no access
P70	writing	writing	no access
P71	writing	writing	no access
P72	writing	writing	no access
P73	writing	writing	no access
P74	writing	writing	no access
P75	writing	writing	no access
P76	writing	writing	no access
P77	writing	writing	no access
P78	writing	writing	no access
P79	writing	writing	no access
P80	writing	writing	no access
P81	writing	writing	no access
P82	writing	writing	no access
P83	writing	writing	no access

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P84	writing	writing	no access
P85	writing	writing	no access
P86	writing	writing	no access
P87	writing	writing	no access
P88	writing	writing	no access
P89	writing	writing	no access
P90	writing	writing	no access
P91	writing	writing	no access
P92	writing	writing	no access
P93	writing	writing	no access
P94	writing	writing	no access
P95	writing	writing	no access
P96	writing	writing	no access
P97	writing	writing	no access
P98	writing	writing	no access
P99	writing	writing	no access
P100	writing	writing	no access
P101	writing	writing	no access
P102	writing	writing	no access
P103	writing	writing	no access
P104	writing	writing	no access
P105	writing	writing	no access
P106	writing	writing	no access
P107	writing	writing	no access
P108	writing	writing	no access

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P109	writing	writing	no access
P110	writing	writing	no access
P111	writing	writing	no access
P112	writing	writing	no access
P113	writing	writing	no access
P114	writing	writing	no access
P115	writing	writing	no access
P116	writing	writing	no access
P117	writing	writing	no access
P118	writing	writing	no access
P119	writing	writing	no access
P120	writing	writing	no access
P121	writing	writing	no access
P122	writing	writing	no access
P123	writing	writing	no access
P124	writing	writing	no access
R1	writing	writing	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P2	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P3	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P4	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P5	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P6	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P7	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P8	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P9	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P10	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P11	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P12	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P13	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P14	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P15	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P16	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P17	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P18	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P19	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P20	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P21	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P22	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P23	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P24	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P25	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P26	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P27	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P28	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P29	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P30	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P31	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P32	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P33	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P34	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P35	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P36	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P37	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P38	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P39	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P40	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P41	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P42	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P43	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P44	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P45	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P46	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P47	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P48	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P49	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P50	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P51	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P52	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P53	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P54	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P55	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P56	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P57	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P58	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P59	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P60	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P61	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P62	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P63	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P64	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P65	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P66	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P67	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P68	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
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P86	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P87	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P88	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P89	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
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P108	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P109	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P110	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P111	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
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P123	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0
P124	Open		2023-05-29			CC BY 4.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: To facilitate data reuse, individuals intending to use the data should have access to Java programming language. Additionally, the raw data provided is available in XML and XLSX formats, enabling users to effectively utilize and reutilize the data.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1		10 years	Decision makers in industry Members of the scientific community
P2		10 years	
P3		10 years	
P4		10 years	
P5		10 years	
P6		10 years	
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P9		10 years	
P10		10 years	
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P121		10 years	
P122		10 years	
P123		10 years	
P124		10 years	

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The lead researcher in charge of this Data Management Plan (DMP) will oversee the overall data management process. The research assistants will be accountable for generating metadata, conducting daily cross-checks, maintaining backups, and performing other quality control activities. The primary researchers from each country will be responsible for regularly supervising the development of the dataset.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

Additional description (if required):